

Enhanced chirality-induced spin polarization in twisted transition metal dichalcogenides

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Summary. — Chirality-induced spin selectivity (CISS) causes electrons in chiral molecules to acquire spin polarization, yet its mechanism remains unclear. This work shows that atomically thin chiral van der Waals crystals, with spin-orbit coupling (SOC), exhibit strong CISS even in bilayers. Calculations for twisted homobilayer Transition Metal Dichalcogenides (TMDs) reveal spin polarization exceeding 20% in MoTe₂. These results establish twisted quantum materials as a tunable platform for CISS in condensed matter physics and chiral chemistry. This manuscript reports a description of these efforts, as illustrated in an oral contribution presented at the SIF Congress 2024 by G. Menichetti.

1. – Introduction

The chirality-induced spin selectivity (CISS) effect, first observed in 1999 by Naaman *et al.* [1], allows chiral molecules to act as spin polarizers. Additionally, CISS can induce enantiospecific chemical processes [2], giving it profound implications for asymmetric chemistry [3]. Despite its significance, its microscopic origin remains unclear (for a recent summary, see ref. [4]), limiting practical applications. A fully tunable platform is needed

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to systematically study the CISS effect, both experimentally and theoretically, under a wide range of control parameters.

We propose twisted moiré superlattices—formed by twisting atomically thin crystals—as ideal systems for this purpose [5]. These materials are naturally chiral and can exhibit spin polarization when spin-orbit coupling is present. In particular, we focus on twisted homobilayer TMDs like MoTe₂, which are known for strong spin-orbit coupling and recent discoveries of exotic quantum states [6].

Twisted materials offer a broad set of tunable parameters, including carrier density, which can be adjusted via the electric field effect, and twist angle. External factors such as temperature and applied magnetic fields also influence electronic band structure, carrier mobility, superconducting transition temperature, and magnetic ordering. This tunability makes them a promising platform for studying the interplay between chirality, spin-orbit coupling, and spin transport. Understanding these effects could advance both fundamental physics and practical applications of the CISS effect.

2. – Setup, scattering matrix, and microscopic modelling

To numerically extract information about the CISS effect in twisted homobilayer TMDs, we use the setup in fig. 1(a), consisting of a twisted H-phase [7]. The reciprocity theorem [8] forbids detecting spin-polarized currents via standard two-terminals magnetoresistance [9], but spin-resolved scattering matrix methods [10] can reveal spin-dependent electron scattering.

The leads provide asymptotic propagating states. We define $\psi_{L,\sigma}^{\text{out}}$ ($\psi_{R,\sigma}^{\text{out}}$) as the wave function of scattered electrons with spin σ into the left (right) lead, and $\psi_{L,\sigma'}^{\text{in}}$ ($\psi_{R,\sigma'}^{\text{in}}$) as incoming wave functions. The system's transport properties are captured by the spin-resolved scattering matrix $S_{\sigma,\sigma'}$:

$$(1) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{L,\sigma}^{\text{out}} \\ \psi_{R,\sigma}^{\text{out}} \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{\sigma'=\uparrow,\downarrow} S_{\sigma,\sigma'} \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{L,\sigma'}^{\text{in}} \\ \psi_{R,\sigma'}^{\text{in}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{where } S_{\sigma,\sigma'} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} r_{\sigma,\sigma'} & t'_{\sigma,\sigma'} \\ t_{\sigma,\sigma'} & r'_{\sigma,\sigma'} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Fig. 1. – (Color online). Panel (a) Sketch of the two-terminal setup studied. A twisted homobilayer TMD in the $\hat{x}\text{-}\hat{y}$ plane is contacted by two semi-infinite leads (gray-shaded areas). The layer separation in the \hat{z} -direction is d , and the top (left) layer is rotated counterclockwise by θ relative to the bottom (right) one. The resulting moiré lattice is plotted on the right. Black arrows indicate spin-resolved reflection ($r_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, $r'_{\sigma,\sigma'}$) and transmission ($t_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, $t'_{\sigma,\sigma'}$) components of the scattering matrix S in eq. (1). Panel (b) Numerical results for the spin polarization $P_t(E)$ from eq. (3). The polarization has opposite signs for θ (red) and $-\theta$ (blue), while it vanishes in the untwisted ($\theta = 0$) case (black dashed line). Parameters correspond to twisted homobilayer MoTe₂ [17] with $\theta = 5.09^\circ$, $\lambda_0 = 220$ meV, and $\lambda_{\text{BR}} = 0$.

Here, $t_{\sigma,\sigma'}, r_{\sigma,\sigma'}$ ($t'_{\sigma,\sigma'}, r'_{\sigma,\sigma'}$) are the spin-resolved transmission and reflection amplitudes of electrons coming from the left (right) lead. All quantities depend on a single energy E , assuming elastic scattering.

From the scattering matrix, we define reflection ($\rho_r, \rho_{r'}$) and transmission ($\rho_t, \rho_{t'}$) density matrices and the dimensionless spin conductances σ_i :

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} \rho_r &\equiv \mathbb{r}\mathbb{r}^\dagger, & \rho_{r'} &\equiv \mathbb{r}'(\mathbb{r}')^\dagger, & \text{and} & \quad \sigma_r &\equiv \text{Tr}[\hat{s}_z \rho_r], & \sigma_{r'} &\equiv \text{Tr}[\hat{s}_z \rho_{r'}] \\ \rho_t &\equiv \mathbb{t}\mathbb{t}^\dagger, & \rho_{t'} &\equiv \mathbb{t}'(\mathbb{t}')^\dagger, & & \quad \sigma_t &\equiv \text{Tr}[\hat{s}_z \rho_t], & \sigma_{t'} &\equiv \text{Tr}[\hat{s}_z \rho_{t'}], \end{aligned}$$

where \hat{s}_z is a Pauli matrix. Here, \mathbb{r} , \mathbb{r}' , \mathbb{t} , and \mathbb{t}' are matrices in spin space with matrix elements $r_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, $r'_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, $t_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, $t'_{\sigma,\sigma'}$, respectively. We focus on σ_t , introducing the energy-dependent chirality-induced spin polarization:

$$(3) \quad P_t(E) = \frac{\sigma_t(E)}{\text{Tr}[\rho_t(E)]} \in [-1, 1].$$

This quantity gives information on the strength of the CISS effect [9, 10] and vanishes when the scatterer is non-chiral.

For what concerns the microscopic modelling of the scatterer, we model the twisted homobilayer TMD using a gapped Dirac-fermion approach [11], incorporating a mass term in a tight-binding Hamiltonian for twisted bilayer graphene (TBG) [12]. Here, given its crucial importance, we focus only on the tight-binding description of SOC in twisted homobilayer TMDs. Among all the possible SOC terms allowed by C_3 symmetry [13], we restrict our analysis to *spin-flipping* nearest-neighbor intra-layer hoppings, since nearest-neighbour and next-nearest-neighbour *spin-conserving* hopping terms yield a vanishing contribution to the CISS strength (3) —consistent with ref. [9].

The SOC Hamiltonian is given by [13]:

$$(4) \quad \hat{\mathcal{H}}_{\text{SOC}}^{(\ell)} = \frac{2i}{3} \lambda_0^{(\ell)} \sum_{\sigma \neq \sigma'} \sum_{\langle (m,\tau), (n,\tau') \rangle} \hat{z} \cdot [\hat{s} \times \mathbf{d}_{m,\tau,n,\tau'}]_{\sigma,\sigma'} |m, \ell, \tau\rangle \langle n, \ell, \tau'| \otimes |\sigma\rangle \langle \sigma'|,$$

where $\ell = 1, 2$ is the layer index, $\lambda_0^{(\ell)} = [\lambda_0 - (-1)^\ell \lambda_{\text{BR}}]$ is the SOC parameter, $\hat{s} = (\hat{s}_x, \hat{s}_y, \hat{s}_z)$ is the Pauli matrix vector, and $\mathbf{d}_{m,\tau,n,\tau'}$ is a unit vector in the \hat{x} - \hat{y} plane pointing from site (n, τ') to (m, τ) . The sum is restricted to nearest neighbors.

Here, λ_0 represents intrinsic intra-layer SOC (as in Bernal-stacked bilayer graphene [14]), while λ_{BR} is the Bychkov-Rashba term arising from broken C_2 symmetry, present even without an external field. Since twisted homobilayer TMDs lack inversion symmetry, inter-layer spin-flip terms exist but are assumed negligible [15]. Notably, for $\lambda_{\text{BR}} = 0$, the system is symmetric under exchange of top/bottom leads and layers, yielding $\sigma_{t'} = -\sigma_t$. For $\lambda_{\text{BR}} \neq 0$, this symmetry is broken.

Despite its simplicity, this model captures both the structural chirality (via the twist angle θ in the intra- and inter-layer terms) and SOC effects, allowing us to explore their interplay in a chiral quasi-2D system.

3. – Numerical results

We present our main numerical results, obtained using Kwant [16] to implement the tight-binding model and compute the spin-resolved scattering matrix $S_{\sigma,\sigma'}$ for the two-terminal setup in fig. 1(a). The leads are semi-infinite A-A stacked graphite, aligned

with adjacent layers of the twisted homobilayer TMD. The spin-resolved $S_{\sigma,\sigma'}$ matrix is integrated over the 2D moiré Brillouin zone.

Figure 1(b) shows the spin polarization $P_t(E)$ for electrons transmitted through twisted MoTe₂ at $\theta = 5.09^\circ$ with SOC parameters $\lambda_0 = 220$ meV and $\lambda_{\text{BR}} = 0$. The spin polarization exceeds 20%, increasing with larger twist angles [17]. As expected, $P_t(E)$ switches sign for θ and $-\theta$ and vanishes for $\theta = 0$. Increasing λ_0 enhances $|P_t(E)|$, emphasizing SOC's crucial role in chirality-induced spin polarization [17].

This effect arises from i) structural chirality and ii) spin-orbit coupling. Electrons injected into the chiral bilayer acquire orbital angular momentum through interlayer tunneling, aligning with the twist direction. SOC couples spin to this motion, inducing spin polarization along \hat{z} , similar to helical molecules [10].

In summary, moiré materials with strong SOC exhibit chirality-induced spin polarization, which can be large even in two twisted monolayers. Our theory, based on a microscopic Hamiltonian, is supported by numerical results for twisted MoTe₂.

Further details, including the evaluation of the CISS effect on other TMDs are reported in ref. [17].

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